

TURKEY'S DELUSION OF THE FIRST 72 HOURS IN COMMUNITY DISASTER PREPAREDNESS

Ali Utku Şahin¹

Keywords

Golden hours,
First 72 hours,
Disaster management,
Disaster preparedness,
Turkey

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to analyze the disaster preparedness and post-disaster activities carried out in Turkey in a comparative context and to re-evaluate these activities in terms of the first 72 hours concept and institutional continuity. This study is prepared by comparative document analysis method. In the study, the disaster preparedness processes of the USA, Japan, and Turkey and their reflections on disaster planning are analyzed and the findings are discussed in terms of the first 72 hours practices and seismicity. The findings show that the first 72 hours in Turkey are mainly evaluated on the axis of individual preparations and that the participation of citizens in the process and institutional service continuity are neglected in both planning and post-disaster implementation processes. It has emerged that the first 72 hours should be handled within a systemic integrity in Turkey's disaster management system and the first 72 hours process should be evaluated especially in terms of institutional service continuity.

INTRODUCTION

The period after the 1999 earthquakes, which is shown as a milestone in the introduction of modern disaster management in Turkey has been named as the "awakening period"¹ in the disaster management literature and has been the period in which radical changes have been put into practice. The "first 72 hours concept", which constitutes the focus of this study, has also entered into the disaster management literature of Turkey in this period. This concept, which is also called "golden hours" in the literature, emphasizes what each member of society, starting from individuals, should do within the first three days following the occurrence of any disaster; more importantly, it emphasizes that they should be self-sufficient. This concept, which can be considered as one of the imported concepts of disaster management, was frequently emphasized after the February 6th, 2023 earthquakes and presented as a prerequisite for being prepared for disasters.

However, in Turkey's disaster management approach, the first 72 hours are mainly associated with individual preparations. In other words, it is symbolized by the right behavioral patterns to be developed in individuals through pre-disaster training and "disaster kit"; whereas the preparations of public institutions and organizations with disaster response responsibilities, business and service continuity, and integration with the hierarchy of plans are hardly mentioned.

This study, which aims to put forward a criticizing approach against this situation, claims to examine the disaster preparations and post-disaster activities carried out in the United States of America (the US), Japan, and Turkey in a comparative manner and to re-evaluate these activities in the axis of the first 72 hours concept and institutional service continuity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, which is prepared by comparative document analysis method, the disaster preparedness processes and their reflections on disaster planning of the US and Japan, two

Volume: 2

Issue: 2

Page: 65-74

Received: 22.02.2024

Accepted: 03.04.2024

Available online: 30.06.2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12673126

countries that have succeeded in becoming models in disaster management, and Turkey have been analyzed.

The findings obtained as a result of these analyses are then discussed with the findings of Turkey in terms of the first 72 hours practices and seismicity scale, with special reference to the sample city practices in the USA and Japan; similarities and differences are evaluated mutually.

FINDINGS

Disaster Preparedness and Practices

In today's modern disaster management concept, there is a consensus that the activities associated with disaster management should be carried out collectively with all members of society. Ergünay² has broadly defined the concept of disaster management as "a multi-actor, multi-disciplinary, multi-comprehensive and complex form of management that requires the use of all institutions and organizations and resources of the society for planning, directing, supporting, coordinating and implementing the activities to be carried out in the four main and other intermediate stages of a disaster event such as mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery to prevent disasters and reduce their damages" and with this definition, he emphasized the structure of disaster management that concerns the whole society.

Disasters are defined as the consequence of a natural or man-made event³. The frequency and severity of disasters have started to increase in parallel with the increase in the urban population on a global scale. In the face of this reality, the modern disaster management approach has started to look for solutions in proactive approaches instead of reactive ones, and finally, risk management has become the dominant field of study in today's disaster management. Risk management and disaster mitigation policies, the first steps of which were taken with the Yokohama Strategy and Plan of Action for a Safer World in 1994, continued with the Hyogo Framework for Action in 2003⁴.

As it is known, modern disaster management consists of four main components that cyclically follow each other. Among these components, "risk and mitigation" and "preparedness and planning" constitute the risk management phase, while "response" and "recovery" constitute the crisis management phase. When these components are evaluated together with the risk management studies developed on a global scale, it can be understood that the studies are carried out within the scope of "risk and mitigation" and "preparedness and planning" components. Today, the activities carried out within the scope of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction, which has been implemented since 2015, continue on a global scale in line with the objectives of understanding disaster risks,

strengthening risk governance, disaster risk reduction investments to ensure resilience, and improving disaster preparedness capacity for effective response and better recovery, rehabilitation and reconstruction processes⁵.

As can be understood from the global studies carried out within the scope of disaster risk reduction and disaster preparedness, there is a consensus throughout the world on the importance of investing in the pre-disaster period. Considering the broad definition of the concept of disaster management, it becomes clear that these studies should cover all levels and segments of society. In this context, being prepared for the "golden hours" that start immediately after the occurrence of disasters constitutes an important part of these efforts.

It can be argued that the approach of being prepared for the first 72 hours or "golden hours" is based on the fact that disaster risks cannot be eliminated, especially in the case of natural disasters. Since there is a potential for a disaster to occur in every situation where a threat element intersects with societal functions, it is as important to be prepared for the "golden hours" starting from the moment the disaster occurs as it is to reduce disaster risks. An approach in this direction can be observed in all societies applying modern disaster management principles. On the practical side of this approach, it can be stated that social disaster awareness training, training on developing the right behavior after the disaster, training on self-sufficiency, first aid, and basic search and rescue activities during the golden hours are common activities⁵.

For example, FEMA, the US agency responsible for disaster management at the federal level, carries out many activities at the national level to reduce disaster risks and prepare for disasters. In this context, the activities under the title of "national preparedness" could be summarized as follows:

- I. Providing information on all types of disasters⁶,
- II. Sharing guidelines for preparing disaster plans for families⁷,
- III. Sharing guidelines on the preparation and content of the disaster kit⁸,
- IV. Encouraging voluntary participation in disaster management⁹,
- V. Sharing guidelines for preparing disaster risk analyses and plans for small and medium-sized enterprises¹⁰,
- VI. Organizing training activities for first responders and disaster managers, as well as individuals and communities¹¹,
- VII. Within the scope of the "citizen responder" concept, supporting the Community Emergency Response Team (CERT) program where basic post-disaster first response skills (response to initial fires, basic search and rescue, first aid applications, etc.) are trained¹².

In Japan, a country with devastating disasters, disaster risk reduction, and disaster preparedness are perceived as a very important task among citizens responsibilities¹³. Disaster preparedness constitutes a part of the education system, and courses on this subject are included in the national curriculum to be taught in schools and are continued throughout society within the concept of lifelong learning^{13,14}.

In Japan's disaster preparedness structure, which is organized into "four types of assistance" (public assistance, self-help, help to neighbors, help to the community), it is ensured that all parts of society, from public authorities to individuals, participate in disaster preparedness efforts; disaster response plans are prepared at all levels, including community and neighborhood levels; workplaces prepare business continuity plans; and volunteer organizations are established for local and community cooperation^{13,15}. In addition, a very high level of social awareness was developed that every home and workplace should have a first aid kit, disaster kit, and food stocks¹³.

In Turkey, activities within the scope of disaster risk reduction and disaster preparedness are carried out and coordinated at the national level by the Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD). Community training and activities carried out within the scope of the Disaster Ready Turkey project and the AFAD Volunteering System are included in these activities.

According to AFAD¹⁶, the purposes of the Disaster Ready Turkey Project are; "to provide all segments of the society, starting with the individual, with the culture of disaster preparedness to be prepared for the first 72 hours of disasters; to raise awareness among individuals; to share with individuals the basic precautions they can take in the places where they live; to ensure that individuals learn and apply the correct behavioral patterns in disaster; to provide information on preparing disaster and emergency plans; to share the basic measures that can be taken; to expand the places where individuals can receive disaster training and to establish infrastructures that they can easily access; to standardize the disaster training given through various channels throughout the country; to benefit from the studies carried out by international organizations and to establish accredited training pathways with sufficient knowledge and experience".

In this context, the activities for risk assessment, risk and mitigation, preparation of disaster and emergency kit, evacuation, school and business disaster management processes, and disaster and emergency planning are carried out for families, workplaces, and schools^{17,18,19}. Additionally, disaster awareness and fire awareness training are provided within the scope of community training²⁰.

Volunteering activities are carried out within the scope of the AFAD Volunteering System established to contribute to the dissemination of disaster preparedness and volunteering awareness in society, to ensure that volunteers gain awareness through the training they receive and spread this awareness around them, to minimize the material and moral damage caused by disasters, to make the society more resilient against disasters and emergencies and to provide a more effective service to communities affected by disasters and emergencies²¹. With the volunteering system defined at three different levels as "Basic", "Support" and "Expert" AFAD Volunteers²², volunteers are trained in areas such as health, nutrition, sheltering, search and rescue needed before, during and after disasters, and are ensured to work effectively at every stage of the disaster²³.

Disaster Preparedness Practices and Integration in Disaster Planning Processes

There is no doubt that the commonalities between the above-mentioned examples of disaster preparedness are striking. However, to "correctly understand" these studies carried out in Turkey together with the USA and Japan, it is necessary to analyze how these activities are integrated into the disaster management system in these countries.

As mentioned before, modern disaster management on a global scale aims to make all parts of society prepared against disasters with an approach focused on risk management and preparedness. The activities carried out in line with this purpose aim to reduce disaster risks on the one hand and to ensure that all parts of the society are self-sufficient and mutually self-sufficient in the first moments after the occurrence of a disaster on the other. However, these objectives cannot be considered separately from the whole disaster management system. In other words, it can be claimed that the success of the practices for the realization of these objectives can only be measured by the existence of other elements that will complement them within the disaster management system.

In the USA, for example, these efforts are carried out from the highest federal level to the individual level, within a specific plan and in a complementary manner. According to the National Planning System²⁴, which constitutes one of the six pillars of the US national preparedness system, the "planning architecture" is designed at three levels as strategic, operational and tactical levels²⁵. The strategic level focuses on long-term strategies and establishes policies; the operational level defines the tasks and responsibilities and the resources required to implement the strategies; and the tactical level defines how the available resources will be used in line with operational objectives within the specified time frame²⁵.

The National Planning System also explains how the plans prepared within the system will be integrated²⁵. For example, the applicability of the family disaster plan, which includes what needs to be done at the family level after a disaster (communication of family members, coming together after a disaster, family safety, etc.), especially on issues such as evacuation, depends on the information to be provided by the local or community emergency plan at the next higher level²⁵.

Within disaster management activities, local or community emergency plans, which cover the activities to be carried out at the local level, and the plans to be prepared by the private sector and non-governmental organizations also function interdependently²⁵. For example, while local plans need the support of the private sector in areas such as media use and meeting the needs of first responders, the private sector also includes in its plans the issues for which it needs support from local authorities²⁵.

A similar approach is reflected in the principles of mitigation and response. As with the National Planning System, the National Mitigation Framework and the National Response Framework are designed to be integrated from the family level to the federal level. In this context, the responsibilities expected from all levels of society in both mitigation and response processes are summarized as follows (Table 1)

Japan, which ensures that disaster management activities are carried out at all levels of the society as in the US, has defined the responsibilities expected from the society not only through planning processes but also through legal regulations. According to Articles 3-7 of the Disaster Countermeasures Basic Act²⁸, which came into force in 1961, the responsibilities of the state, regional prefectures, city/town/village administrations, national and local public organizations, and local people are as follows (Table 2)

These responsibilities defined by law in Japan are also reflected in disaster planning processes. As stated in Table 2, administrations and public institutions at all levels of society are obliged to prepare disaster prevention plans related to their jurisdictions or areas of expertise compatible with the plan at the next higher level²⁸.

In this context, with the Community Disaster Management Planning System implemented in 2013, voluntary participation of local people in disaster management and risk reduction activities and cooperation with local authorities are ensured²⁹. As a result, the Community Disaster Management Plans prepared within this system form a part of the Municipal Disaster Management Plans²⁹.

In 2014, the business continuity planning system, which had previously been implemented for public institutions in the Tokyo region, was expanded to cover the entire country²⁹. This

expanded practice, aims to maintain the functional structure of the entire public authority across the country, including local governments, in the event of a possible disaster; in other words, the entire public administration structure, from the smallest municipality to the government itself, should be able to fulfill its administrative functions and duties²⁹. In the private sector, the business continuity system has been in place since 2005, with an update in 2013²⁹.

In Turkey, disaster management efforts, which gained momentum with the awakening period, are currently carried out based on the Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation, Turkey Disaster Response Plan (TAMP), and Turkey Disaster Risk Reduction Plan. The Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation³⁰, which first came into force in 2013 and was updated in 2022, regulates planning principles at the national and local level, responsibilities, and assignment procedures in disaster situations. According to this regulation, TAMP and national level working group plans are the plans at the national level; provincial disaster response plans and local level working group operation plans are the plans at the local level³⁰. The Regulation also requires the preparation of workplace emergency plans for public and private sector workplaces³⁰.

According to the provisions of the Regulation on duties and responsibilities, public institutions and organizations under the central administration, local administrations, autonomous public institutions, provincial administrations, and individuals are assigned various duties and responsibilities³⁰. Accordingly, AFAD is responsible for general coordination, ministries, and autonomous public institutions are responsible for the planning and execution of activities in their areas of expertise, local authorities are responsible for coordination at the provincial and district level, and individuals are responsible for fulfilling the duties assigned to them following their situation³⁰. In addition to the fulfillment of the tasks assigned to them in the working groups to which they are assigned³¹, local governments are responsible for the identification of disaster and emergency assembly areas according to the criteria determined by the responsible working group and the preparation of temporary shelter areas and their infrastructure³¹.

Updated in 2022, TAMP defines the disaster response organization at the national and local levels. Accordingly, the duties and responsibilities assigned to the working groups defined in TAMP and the responsible institutions of each working group are as follows (Table 3)

Evaluation: Do We Understand The Concept of The First 72 Hours Correctly?

Table 1. Community Responsibilities in Mitigation and Response – the US

	Mitigation	Response
Individuals and Families	Preparing a family disaster plan and disaster kit; taking necessary precautions against fire, tornadoes, floods, and power outages, vaccination	To reduce the potential need for intervention in the aftermath of a disaster by making preparations beforehand, to be self-sufficient until help arrives, to follow the instructions of the authorities
Communities	Bridging the gap between local people and authorities, identifying community-specific risks and needs	To help stabilize social activities in the aftermath of a disaster, and to ensure that the expertise of its members is utilized
Non-Governmental Organizations	Representing their grassroots in the formulation of mitigation policies, disseminating the preparatory work throughout the country through the groups they represent	Managing volunteers and donations, identifying shelters and supporting evacuation, meeting urgent needs such as water and food, supporting response efforts, and providing necessary support to disaster victims
Private Sector Businesses	Managing their risks through business analysis, taking part in services needed in disasters, operating workplace disaster management centers, improving business continuity	Determining their response capacities, providing the necessary support in cooperation with the authorities after the disaster as agreed in advance, ensuring business continuity
Local Governments	Taking measures to reduce long-term vulnerability, determining mitigation policy, determining recovery policies	To implement the local disaster management program, to carry out necessary response activities after disasters, to coordinate resource needs
States	Determining and implementing mitigation policies in their jurisdictions, building bridges between local governments and federal units, making legal arrangements related to mitigation	Implementing the tasks assigned by state law, informing the public, providing the necessary technical support, implementing the volunteer and donation management plan, coordinating with local governments, commanding the military units under its jurisdiction
Federal Government	Ensure coordination and integration of all mitigation processes from communities to states	Declaring an emergency according to requests from the states, coordinating federal resources, and transferring the necessary resources to the region where the emergency is declared

Source: Prepared by the author using ^{26, 27}

Table 2. Responsibilities according to the Disaster Countermeasures Basic Act - Japan

	Disaster Responsibilities
State	To prepare a plan that will form the basis for disaster prevention, emergency measures, and post-disaster rehabilitation processes; to ensure that activities related to the prevention of disasters are carried out by local administrations, public institutions, and others deemed necessary; to ensure general coordination related to disaster management
Regional Prefectures	To make and implement the disaster prevention plan within its jurisdiction together with other institutions involved in disaster management; to support local administrations and public institutions at its lower level in carrying out activities related to the prevention of disasters; to ensure general coordination
City/Town/Village Administrations	To make and implement the disaster prevention plan within its jurisdiction together with other institutions involved in disaster management; to work in coordination with local administrations and public institutions in the execution of activities related to the prevention of disasters; to make the best use of all the capacity of the city for disasters; to ensure the establishment of volunteer organizations and their support for activities
National and Local Public Organizations	To prepare disaster prevention plans related to their areas of specialization or the activities they carry out; to participate in disaster management activities related to their areas of specialization and to cooperate with administrative authorities
Local People	To fulfill the duties assigned to them in the plans related to disaster prevention; to contribute to disaster prevention activities by taking individual measures; to participate in disaster prevention activities by taking part in voluntary organizations

Source: Prepared by the author using [28]

Table 3. Working Groups, Responsible Institutions, and Duties in TAMP

Working Group	Responsible Institution	Duty
Disaster Communication Group	Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure	Maintaining uninterrupted and secure communication at national and local levels in disasters and emergencies
Disaster Energy Group	Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources	Ensuring that these services return to normal as soon as possible by making emergency repairs of power lines such as electricity, natural gas, etc. in the disaster area
Disaster Security and Traffic Group	Ministry of Interior	Ensuring security and regular flow of traffic in disasters and emergencies
Disaster Fire Group	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Carrying out intervention activities for fires occurring in disasters and emergencies
Disaster Search and Rescue Group	AFAD	Carrying out search and rescue services in disasters and emergencies, intervention activities related to CBRN incidents, supporting intervention activities related to hazardous substances
Disaster Medical Group	Ministry of Health	Ensuring that the first medical intervention, public health, and medical care needs at the scene of disasters and emergencies are met and that environmental health services return to normal in the fastest way without disruption
Disaster Evacuation and Relocation Planning Group	Ministry of Interior	Planning, implementation, and placement of evacuation before, during, and after the disaster
Disaster Transport Group	Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure	Transportation of personnel, disaster victims, and resources in disasters and emergencies
Disaster Transportation Group	Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure	Ensuring the fastest and safest transportation to the disaster area in disasters and emergencies and making navigation arrangements
Disaster Sheltering Group	AFAD	Carrying out emergency and temporary shelter services for disaster victims in the disaster area
Disaster Infrastructure Group	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Identifying the damage to water, sewerage treatment plant, etc. lines in the disaster area and having them repaired immediately and ensuring that these services return to normal as soon as possible
Disaster Damage Assessment Group	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Immediate determination of the approximate extent of preliminary damage to infrastructure (water, sewerage, treatment, etc.) and building stock in the disaster area and carrying out damage assessment services
Disaster Nutrition Group	Turkish Red Crescent	Provision of nutrition services in the disaster area
Disaster Psychosocial Support Group	Ministry of Family and Social Services	Providing psychosocial support services to disaster victims in the disaster area
Disaster Debris Removal Group	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Removal of debris in the disaster area
Disaster Agriculture Forestry Food Water and Livestock Group	Ministry of Agriculture and Forest	In case of disasters and emergencies, carrying out damage assessment of the affected agricultural areas, ensuring food safety and carrying out the necessary work on the health of deceased, culled and affected animals, supplying and transporting potable water until the completion of infrastructure works in the disaster area, drilling water wells in sufficient number when necessary
Disaster Identification and Burial Group	Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change	Burial of the deceased in disasters and emergencies
Disaster Information Management, Assessment and Monitoring Group	AFAD	Collecting, recording, and reporting all kinds of information related to disasters and emergencies and evaluating, monitoring, and reporting the information obtained in response activities and transmitting the information to the relevant units
Disaster Communication Group	Directorate of Communications and AFAD	Ensuring healthy information flow by organizing relations with written, visual, and digital media elements to inform the public correctly regarding disasters and emergencies
Disaster Donations, Warehouse Management and Distribution Group	Ministry of Family and Social Services	Collection, warehouse services, and distribution of in-kind donations made to disaster victims
Disaster Technical Support and Supply Group	Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure	Providing maintenance, repair, refueling, and support for all kinds of machinery and vehicles used in disasters and emergencies
Disaster International Support and Cooperation Group	AFAD	Coordinating international support to be provided
Disaster Finance and Resource Management Group	AFAD	Procurement and monitoring of additional personnel, technical experts, materials, and equipment to work in disasters and emergencies, procurement and leasing services within the scope of emergency aid expenditures, and accounting, budget, and financial reporting services
Disaster National and International Cash Donation Group	AFAD	Coordinating national and international cash donation services
Disaster Loss Assessment Group	Ministry of Treasury and Finance	Determining the financial and economic dimension of damages related to disasters and emergencies

Source: Prepared by the author using ³¹

As mentioned before, since there is a potential for a disaster to emerge in every situation where a threat element intersects with social activities, it is important to be prepared for the "golden hours" starting from the moment the disaster occurs. This is because it is accepted that those who are in the place where the disaster occurs will be on their own for the first 72 hours³². However, the importance of the first 72 hours is not only due to the principle of self-sufficiency during this period. Since the concept of the first 72 hours also covers all the elements of the community experiencing the disaster, it also means that the community starts to respond to the disaster with all the resources it has³². UN OCHA also states that the first 72 hours after a disaster is the most critical period and that rescue operations should start in this period³³, and the findings of a recently published study show once again the importance of the first 72 hours by stating that rescue operations should be completed within the first 24 hours for 75% life-saving success after an earthquake³⁴. In this respect, it is important to evaluate the concept of the first 72 hours in terms of both individual/family and organizational preparedness and capacity.

When preparations for the first 72 hours are evaluated at the individual and family level, it can be stated that both the US and Japan have similar practices. In both countries, preparations to be carried out at the individual and family level are given importance and these activities are encouraged by the authorities³⁴.

For example, according to the State Emergency Plan of the state of California, one of the riskiest regions of the US in terms of earthquakes, residents of the state make a significant contribution to disaster management by preparing for disasters³⁵. Accordingly, the people who receive first aid training before the disaster, procure the materials they will use in case of an emergency in advance, and prepare to evacuate or to be self-sufficient by staying where they are for a few days are expected to act according to the directions from the authorities after the disaster³⁵.

In line with the US disaster management planning system, expectations from citizens at the state level are further elaborated at the local level. For example, according to the Emergency Operations Plan of the city of Los Angeles, the largest city in the state of California with over 3.5 million inhabitants³⁶, it is assumed that the inhabitants of the city will be self-sufficient³⁷. According to this assumption, the inhabitants will stock seven days' worth of food, about 12 liters of water per day for each family member, and enough medical supplies; they will also have prepared family disaster plans; in addition, individuals, local communities, volunteer organizations and businesses will support post-disaster efforts³⁷.

In Japan, where the earthquake risk is high, the preparations to be made by individuals and families are determined by the authorities and shared with the public in detail. For example, the information prepared by the Tokyo Metropolitan Area Government explains in detail how to stock up on food and water, how to prepare an emergency kit, how to reduce non-structural risks within the house, how to prepare for evacuation, and how to cooperate with neighbors³⁸.

According to the information guidelines, the preparations asked from the citizens are as follows:

- I. To stockpile specified quantities of supplies that will be needed after the disaster, including food and water, medicine, and hygiene supplies³⁸,
- II. To prepare an emergency kit with a minimum level of equipment to meet needs such as personal safety, lighting, food, heating, and first aid³⁸,
- III. To reduce non-structural risks in their homes by securing their belongings³⁸,
- IV. To learn about their neighborhood and identify evacuation areas to prepare for evacuation³⁸,
- V. To learn about environmental risks in their neighborhood³⁸,
- VI. To determine how to communicate and cooperate with the people around them³⁸.

Evacuation and sheltering are another important issues that concerns the individual and family in the aftermath of a disaster. It can be stated that there are differences between the practices in the US and Japan in this regard. For example, according to the Mass Care and Sheltering Annex of the Emergency Operations Plan of the city of Los Angeles³⁹, only 10% of the population affected by the disaster will need shelter in predetermined areas. In the annexes of the plan, it is determined how the evacuation will be carried out in case of need⁴⁰, which predetermined sheltering areas will be activated following which procedure, and which services will be provided to whom in these areas^{41,42}.

In Japan, citizens are advised to leave their neighborhoods in case of danger and go to a temporary evacuation area³⁸. These areas are usually a nearby school building or a park, but in case it becomes dangerous, they are advised to go to pre-prepared evacuation areas (disaster prevention parks) to meet needs such as cooking and toilets³⁸. In the case of temporary shelters, a total of 4200 evacuation centers (temporary shelters) with predetermined operating conditions are kept ready for use in the Tokyo Metropolitan Area⁴³.

In Japan, citizens are advised to leave their neighborhoods in case of danger and go to a temporary evacuation area³⁸. These areas are usually a nearby school building or a park, but in case it becomes dangerous, they are advised to go to pre-prepared evacuation areas (disaster prevention parks) to meet needs such as cooking and toilets³⁸. In the case of temporary

shelters, a total of 4200 evacuation centers (temporary shelters) with predetermined operating conditions are kept ready for use in the Tokyo Metropolitan Area⁴⁴.

When the preparations for the first 72 hours are evaluated in terms of institutional capacity, it is understood that both the US and Japan have a similar preparedness structure. In the US, since local resources are expected to be able to manage the first 72 hours⁴⁴, "continuity plans" are defined at the state level³⁵. As mentioned earlier, Japan follows a similar practice, ensuring that the entire public administration structure can fulfill its administrative functions and duties²⁹.

Preparations for the first 72 hours in Turkey have similarities and differences with the examples of the US and Japan. In preparations carried out at the individual and family level, AFAD recommends the preparation of a family disaster plan and a disaster bag with differences in content, as in the US and Japan. However, apart from these similarities, it should be noted that there are differences and even deficiencies, especially in terms of evacuation and sheltering, neighborhood preparations, and institutional capacity.

As mentioned earlier, both in the US and Japan, the areas to be used for the evacuation and temporary sheltering of citizens have been predetermined and the necessary infrastructures have been prepared. In Turkey, however, only assembly areas have been designated, and the infrastructure and adequacy of these areas, especially in Istanbul, are controversial⁴⁵.

A similar situation can be expressed concerning neighborhood preparations. In both the US and Japan, local people participate in local planning activities and support response activities voluntarily. However, since disaster management plans in Turkey are prepared at the national and provincial levels, planning at the neighborhood scale is not carried out (See Article 8 of the Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation). The volunteering activities carried out within the previously mentioned AFAD Volunteering System are coordinated by AFAD provincial directorates and carried out on a national scale, thus differing from local volunteering practices in the US and Japan²³.

It can be stated that there is a similar situation for the preparations made in terms of institutional capacity in Turkey. Although many public institutions and organizations have been assigned duties in disaster response activities by both TAMP and the Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation, the service continuity of these institutions and organizations has not been mentioned. Workplace Emergency Plans referred to in Article 10 of the Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation are plans that define what should be done in case of an emergency that may occur in the workplace⁴⁶ and do not have the quality of a plan for

continuity of service mentioned in this study. This issue has also been the subject of another study⁴⁷.

CONCLUSION

As the information provided so far in this study shows, there are differences between the US, Japan, and Turkey in the understanding and implementation of the concept of the first 72 hours in disaster preparedness processes. In the US and Japan, the first 72 hours are not only understood as preparations to be made at the individual/family levels but also understood and implemented as a process in which individuals will participate in post-disaster activities as communities and institutions will take part by ensuring service continuity.

However, in Turkey, the first 72 hours are predominantly evaluated on the axis of individual preparations and the participation of citizens in the process and institutional service continuity are neglected in both planning and post-disaster implementation processes. This situation causes the burden especially in the first 72 hours to shift to individual/family preparations and negatively affects the success in this period, which is referred to as the "golden hours" after the disaster. In this respect, the first 72 hours should be handled within systemic integrity in Turkey's disaster management system. For that reason, the recommendations are stated as follows:

- I. Ensuring that assembly area infrastructures meet the needs of the first 72 hours,
- II. Identifying temporary shelter areas in advance, preparing their infrastructure, and publicizing them,
- III. First response capacity at the local level should be analyzed on the axis of "service continuity" and deficiencies should be eliminated,
- IV. Increasing voluntary first responder capacity at the local level,
- V. Ensuring the active participation of local people in the preparation of response plans in areas of concern to them,
- VI. Ensuring integration between disaster response plans according to their levels.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

Acknowledgements

No

REFERENCES

1. Japan International Cooperation Agency, Türkiye'de Doğal Afetler Konulu Ülke Strateji Raporu [Strategic Report on Natural Disasters in Turkey], Ankara: Japan International Cooperation Agency, 2004.

2. O. Ergünay, "Afet Yönetiminde İşbirliği ve Koordinasyonun Önemi [The Importance of Colaboration and Coordination in Disaster Management]," in Afet Yönetiminin Temel İlkeleri, M. Kadioğlu and E. Özdamar, Eds., Ankara, Japonya Uluslararası İşbirliği Ajansı Türkiye Ofisi, 2005, pp. 9-18.
3. UNISDR, Terminology on Disaster Risk Reduction, Geneva: United Nations, 2009.
4. İ. Macit, "The Anticipated Effects of Sendai Framework Action Plan in Integrated Disaster Management," Journal of Natural Hazards and Environment, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 175-186, 2019.
5. UNISDR, "Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 - 2030," United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Redcution, 2015. [Online]. Available: https://www.unisdr.org/files/43291_sendaiframeworkfordrren.pdf. [Accessed 10 02 2024].
6. FEMA, "Disasters and Emergencies," 2024a. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ready.gov/be-informed>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
7. FEMA, "Make A Plan," 2024b. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ready.gov/plan>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
8. FEMA, "Build A Kit," 2024c. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ready.gov/kit>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
9. FEMA, "Get Involved," 2024d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ready.gov/get-involved>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
10. FEMA, "Ready Business," 2024e. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ready.gov/business>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
11. FEMA, "Training and Education," 2024f. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fema.gov/emergency-preparedness/training>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
12. FEMA, "What is CERT?," 2024g. [Online]. Available: https://community.fema.gov/PreparednessCommunity/s/about-cert?language=en_US. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
13. K. Kitagawa, "Disaster preparedness, adaptive politics and lifelong learning: a case of Japan," International Journal of Lifelong Education, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 629-647, 2016.
14. K. Kitagawa, "Continuity and Change in Disaster Education in Japan," History of Education, pp. 371-390, 2015.
15. Cabinet Office, "White Paper Disaster Management in Japan," 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.bousai.go.jp/en/documentation/white_paper/index.html. [Accessed 22 02 2024].
16. AFAD, "Afete Hazır Türkiye Projesi [Disaster Ready Turkey]," 2024a. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afete-hazir-turkiye-projesi>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
17. AFAD, "Afete Hazır Aile [Disaster Ready Family]," 2024b. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afadem/afete-hazir-aile>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
18. AFAD, "Afete Hazır Okul [Disaster Ready School]," 2024c. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afadem/afete-hazir-okul>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
19. AFAD, "Afete Hazır İşyeri [Disaster Ready Business]," 2024d. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afadem/afete-hazir-isyeri>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
20. AFAD, "Toplum Eğitimleri [Community Training]," 2024e. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afadem/toplum-egitimleri>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
21. AFAD, "AFAD Gönüllülük Sistemi İle Neleri Hedefliyoruz? [Purpose of AFAD Volunteering System]," 2024f. [Online]. Available: <https://gonullu.afad.gov.tr>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
22. AFAD, "AFAD Gönüllüsü Gönüllülük Seviyeleri [Ranks of AFAD Volunteers]," 2024g. [Online]. Available: <https://gonullu.afad.gov.tr>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
23. AFAD, "AFAD Gönüllülük Projesi [AFAD Volunteering Project]," 2024h. [Online]. Available: <https://www.afad.gov.tr/afad-gonulluluk-projesi>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
24. FEMA, "National Preparedness System," 2024h. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fema.gov/emergency-managers/national-preparedness/system>. [Accessed 20 02 2024].
25. FEMA, "National Planning System," 2016a. [Online]. Available: https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-04/National_Planning_System_20151029.pdf. [Accessed 21 02 2024].
26. FEMA, "National Mitigation Framework," 2016b. [Online]. Available: https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-04/National_Mitigation_Framework2nd_june2016.pdf. [Accessed 24 02 2024].
27. FEMA, "National Response Framework," 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.fema.gov/sites/default/files/2020-04/NRF_FINALApproved_2011028.pdf. [Accessed 24 02 2024].
28. National Land Agency, "Disaster Countermeasures Basic Act," 1997. [Online]. Available: <https://www.adrc.asia/documents/law/DisasterCountermeasuresBasicAct.pdf>. [Accessed 23 02 2024].

29. Cabinet Office, "White Paper Disaster Management in Japan," 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.bousai.go.jp/en/documentation/white_paper/pdf/2022/R4_hakusho_english.pdf. [Accessed 24 02 2024].
30. "Disaster and Emergency Response Services Regulation," 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.resmigazete.gov.tr/eskiler/2022/02/20220224-31.pdf>. [Accessed 24 02 2024].
31. AFAD, "Türkiye Afet Müdahale Planı [National Disaster Response Plan of Turkey]," 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.afad.gov.tr/kurumlar/afad.gov.tr/e_Kutuphane/Planlar/TAMP.pdf. [Accessed 25 02 2024].
32. M. O'Leary, "Introduction: What is SEMP?," in *The First 72 Hours: A Community Approach to Disaster Preparedness*, M. O'Leary, Ed., iUniverse, Inc, 2004, pp. 1-29.
33. UN OCHA, "5 essentials for the first 72 hours of disaster response," 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unocha.org/publications/report/world/5-essentials-first-72-hours-disaster-response>. [Accessed 27 02 2024].
34. N. Hooshangi, N. M. Gharakhanlou and S. R. Ghaffari-Razin, "Urban search and rescue (USAR) simulation in earthquake environments using queuing theory: estimating the appropriate number of rescue teams," *International Journal of Disaster Resilience in the Built Environment*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 1-18, 2024.
35. "State of California Emergency Plan," 2017. [Online]. Available: https://www.caloes.ca.gov/wp-content/uploads/Preparedness/Documents/California_State_Emergency_Plan_2017.pdf. [Accessed 28 02 2024].
36. World Population Review, "The 200 Largest Cities in the United States by Population 2024," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/us-cities>. [Accessed 28 02 2024].
37. "City of Los Angeles Base Emergency Operations Plan," 2023. [Online]. Available: https://emergency.lacity.gov/sites/g/files/wph1791/files/2023-10/Emergency%20Operations%20Base%20Plan_2023.pdf. [Accessed 28 02 2024].
38. Tokyo Metropolitan Government, "Let's Get Prepared Disaster Preparedness Actions," 2024a. [Online]. Available: https://www.bousai.metro.tokyo.lg.jp/book/pdf/en/02_Lets_Get_Prepared.pdf. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
39. "Mass Care and Sheltering Annex," 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://emergency.lacity.gov/sites/g/files/wph1791/files/2022-09/Mass%20Care%20and%20Shelter%20Annex%20%282020%29.pdf>. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
40. "Evacuation Functional Support Annex," 2018. [Online]. Available: https://emergency.lacity.gov/sites/g/files/wph1791/files/2021-04/evacuation_annex_2018.pdf. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
41. "Traditional Sheltering Appendix," 2018. [Online]. Available: files/2021-04/mass_care_-_trad_sheltering_appendix_2018.pdf. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
42. "Non-Traditional Sheltering Appendix," 2018. [Online]. Available: https://emergency.lacity.gov/sites/g/files/wph1791/files/2021-04/mass_care_-_nontrad_shelter_2018.pdf. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
43. Tokyo Metropolitan Government, "Simulation of a Major Earthquake," 2024b. [Online]. Available: https://www.bousai.metro.tokyo.lg.jp/book/pdf/en/01_Simulation_of_a_Major_Earthquake.pdf. [Accessed 01 03 2024].
44. H. H. de Anda, C. L. Freeman and S. Braithwaite, "EMS Criteria For Disaster Declaration," in *StatPearls, Treasure Island (FL)*, StatPearls Publishing, 2022.
45. H. E. Uyar and E. Özkan, "The First Stop After the Earthquake: A research of the Gathering Areas in Istanbul," *Journal of Disaster and Risk*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 226-242, 2023.
46. "Regulation of Emergency Situations in Workplaces," 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/mevzuat?MevzuatNo=18493&MevzuatTur=7&MevzuatTertip=5>. [Accessed 02 03 2024].
47. A. U. Şahin, "Evaluation of the Turkey's National Disaster Response Plan from the Point of Disaster Management and Disaster Planning," *Resilience Journal*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 129-158, 2020.